

Practical Sliding-Mode Control for Impulsive Switched Systems with State-Dependent Jump Times

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Abstract

This paper proposes a practical sliding-mode control framework for nonlinear input-affine state-dependent impulsive switched systems whose impulse times arise as state-dependent perturbations of predefined time intervals. Under standard regularity conditions on the sliding manifolds and a decomposition into sliding and internal states, we derive a sufficient lower bound on the control input that guarantees reachability of a prescribed sliding tube and its practical invariance in the presence of state-triggered jumps and matched uncertainties. A weighted mode-dependent average dwell-time condition is established to ensure global exponential stability of a time-dependent comparison system governing the internal dynamics. For internal dynamics expressible as convex combinations of linear subsystems, we provide LMI-based certification conditions. An automated heuristic linear manifold-design algorithm is further proposed to seek sliding manifolds that ensure practical stability and exclude beating phenomena. A numerical example illustrates the effectiveness of the method in stabilizing systems with state-dependent jumps, matched model uncertainties and disturbances.

Keywords: Hybrid systems, state-dependent impulsive switched systems, sliding-mode control, average dwell time, linear matrix inequalities

1. Introduction

We consider the state-dependent impulsive switched system

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}(t) &= f_{\sigma_i}(x, t) + g_{\sigma_i}(x, t) u_{\sigma_i}(x, t), & (t, x) \notin \Gamma_i, \\ x(t^+) &= x(t^-) + J_{\sigma_{i+1}}(x(t^-)), & (t, x) \in \Gamma_i, \\ x(t_0^+) &= x_0 \in \mathbb{R}^n. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The switching signal $\sigma : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ is piecewise constant and right-continuous, with $\sigma_i := \sigma(\xi_i^+)$ on each interval $[\xi_i, \xi_{i+1})$. A strictly increasing nominal grid $\{\theta_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ is given, and the actual event times satisfy $\xi_i \in [\theta_i, \theta_{i+1})$, $\xi_i = \theta_i + \tau_i(x(\xi_i^-))$, where $\tau_i : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is continuously differentiable. Equivalently, each discontinuity surface is $\Gamma_i := \{(t, x) : t = \theta_i + \tau_i(x)\}$. For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$ we assume $f_m : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, $g_m : \mathbb{R}^n \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n \times r}$ are locally Lipschitz in x and measurable in t , and jumps are defined by $J_m : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$. The input applied in mode m is $u_m(x, t) = u_m^c(x, t) + d_m(x, t)$, $u_m(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$, where u_m^c is the control input and d_m represents matched uncertainties and disturbances. Throughout, trajectories are taken to be right-continuous with left limits (càdlàg).

Our objective is to design a practical sliding-mode controller for this class of state-dependent impulsive systems such that the origin is practically asymptotically stable, i.e., all trajectories enter and remain in a prescribed neighborhood of the origin.

Many engineering and physical systems exhibit *hybrid* behavior, i.e., a combination of continuous-time evolution (described by ODEs) and discrete events (modeled as instantaneous state jumps).

Figure 1: Original trajectory $x(t)$ and its B-equivalent $\hat{x}(t)$, showing state-dependent and fixed jumps. The manifold Γ_i defines the state-triggered impulse time ξ_i .

Consider $M \subset \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \times \mathbb{R}^n$ as a given event set. In a general impulsive hybrid system, the state $x : [t_0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ evolves according to $\dot{x} = f(x, t)$, $(t, x(t)) \notin M$, and undergoes jumps whenever $(t, x(t^-)) \in M$, where the jump relation specifies $x(t^+)$ as a function of $x(t^-)$ and possibly t . Analyzing such systems in full generality is challenging, and it is common to classify them into the following subclasses.

(i) *Fixed-time-dependent impulses:* The event set is

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of the form $M = \{(t, x) : t = \theta_i, \theta_i \in \Omega\}$, so all trajectories experience jumps only at the prescribed instants $\{\theta_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$; see Fig. 1. This corresponds to time-scheduled impulses.

(ii) *State-dependent impulses*: The event set is given by $M = \{(t, x) : t = \tau_i(x)\}$, so each trajectory encounters jumps at state-dependent times ξ_i satisfying $\xi_i = \tau_i(x(\xi_i^-))$, as illustrated in Fig. 1. Different solutions generally jump at different instants.

(iii) *Autonomous discontinuous systems*: In the time-invariant case, one often considers an autonomous system $\dot{x} = f(x)$ with a discontinuity surface $M = \{(t, x) : \gamma(x) = 0\}$, so that jumps occur whenever x reaches the manifold $\{x : \gamma(x) = 0\}$.

In this paper we consider a special subclass of state-dependent impulsive systems in which each jump occurs within a prescribed time window, $\xi_i(x) \in [\theta_i, \theta_{i+1})$, where θ_i is a known nominal impulse schedule (anchors). The actual event time is modeled as a state-dependent perturbation of the anchor, $\xi_i(x) = \theta_i + \tau_i(x)$. Many practical hybrid systems fall into this structure. Impulsive actions are often organized around a nominal clock or operating cycle, while the precise jump time within each cycle is determined by the state. Examples include power converters with cycle-by-cycle current limiting, event- and self-triggered networked control built on periodic sampling grids, biological and epidemiological models with seasonal intervention windows, and state-dependent impulsive neural networks under periodic excitation.

Hybrid and impulsive systems have been extensively studied, including stability analysis [1, 2, 3, 4, 5], controllability [6], observer design [7, 8, 9], and control [10, 11]. Akhmet [12] formalized the special class of state-dependent impulsive systems with impulses occurring between known time intervals and introduced the B-equivalent transformation, which converts a state-dependent system into a time-dependent impulsive system. Under suitable regularity and no-beating conditions, stability of the time-dependent model carries over to the original system. These ideas have been applied, e.g., to neural networks [13], delayed impulsive systems [14], and other nonlinear hybrid dynamics [15].

Sliding-mode control (SMC) has also been widely investigated for time-dependent impulsive systems [16, 17, 18, 19], but its use for *state-dependent* impulses remains essentially unexplored. Moreover, most existing SMC schemes enforce ideal sliding ($s = 0$) and therefore, neglect jumps of the sliding variable, an assumption that is often incompatible with bounded actuators.

We consider a nonlinear input-affine state-dependent impulsive switched system (1) with matched disturbances and bounded control input. The goal is to design a practical sliding-mode controller that (i) drives the mode-dependent sliding variable $s_m(x)$ toward its manifold $\mathcal{S}_m := \{x : s_m(x) = 0\}$, (ii) guarantees

invariance of a prescribed tube $\|s_m(x)\| \leq \Delta^*$ in the presence of state-dependent jumps, and (iii) ensures practical asymptotic stability of the full hybrid system.

The design explicitly accounts for the fact that in practice the sliding variable cannot be maintained exactly on the manifold, and that impulses may induce jumps in $s_m(x)$ itself. The controller and analysis are therefore formulated in terms of *practical sliding* in a tube $\|s\| \leq \Delta^*$, rather than ideal sliding on \mathcal{S}_m . No special parametric structure of the jump maps is required, and the sliding manifolds are free design variables as long as standard reachability and regularity conditions hold. Also, unlike ideal SMC schemes based on discontinuous sign laws, we employ a continuous saturation-based reaching law. Technically, the main contributions are as follows.

- We derive mode-dependent sliding variables and a correction law that guarantee finite-time reachability of a prescribed tube $\|s\| \leq \Delta$ and invariance of an enlarged tube $\|s\| \leq \Delta^*$ for nonlinear state-dependent impulsive switched systems. The analysis provides explicit conditions on a minimum control input to prevent accumulation of jump effects.
- We tailor the B-equivalent framework [12] to our setting to relate the nominal internal dynamics to the original internal dynamics in (s, z) -coordinates. Exponential stability of a time-dependent comparison system for the nominal internal dynamics, combined with the practical sliding result, yields practical exponential stability of the original state-dependent impulsive switched system.
- We establish a weighted, mode-dependent average dwell-time condition for exponential stability of the nominal time-dependent comparison system. The condition allows genuinely unstable modes as long as their weighted activation time is sufficiently small, and is expressed in terms of mode-dependent Lyapunov decay rates.
- For internal dynamics that admit a polytopic representation, we provide an LMI-based synthesis and certification procedure: the method jointly computes Lyapunov matrices and linear mode-dependent sliding manifolds such that the stability condition holds and a no-beating condition is satisfied.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 introduces the hybrid model in sliding-internal coordinates (s, z) and the standing assumptions. Section 3 develops the practical sliding-mode control law and establishes reachability and tube invariance under impulses. Section 4 formulates the comparison system. Section 5 presents the weighted mode-dependent average dwell-time condition and the LMI-based design for systems representable as convex combinations of linear subsystems. Section 6 reports a numerical example, and Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. Mathematical Setting and Assumptions

We begin by introducing the notation used throughout the paper. After defining the required properties of the mode-dependent sliding manifolds, we present a coordinate decomposition of the system into sliding and internal states. For this decomposed system, we then impose the standing assumptions on the dynamics and on the state-dependent discontinuity surfaces Γ_i .

2.1. Notation

The active mode immediately after the i th jump is denoted $\sigma_i := \sigma(\xi_i^+)$. For any quantity X , the notations X_i^- and X_i^+ refer to its values immediately before and after the i th jump. The set \mathcal{B}_r is the Euclidean ball of radius r centered at the origin, and \mathcal{T}_r is a tube of radius r . The symbol C^\dagger denotes the Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse, and $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the Euclidean norm. A hat $\hat{\cdot}$ indicates objects associated with the B-equivalent system. We use $e_1 = [1 \ 0 \ 0]$.

2.2. Sliding Manifold

For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, let $s_m : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^r$ be a smooth function defining the sliding manifold $\mathcal{S}_m := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : s_m(x) = 0\}$. The control objective is to drive the trajectory of (1) into the prescribed sliding tube $\mathcal{T}_{\Delta^*} := \{x : \|s_m(x)\| \leq \Delta^*\}$ in finite time for some m , and to maintain practical invariance of this tube for all subsequent modes. On \mathcal{S}_m , the constraint $s_m(x) = 0$ induces an $(n-r)$ -dimensional internal dynamics. The sliding manifolds are required to satisfy the regularity and reachability conditions specified next.

Definition 1. For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, let $s_m : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^r$ be a C^1 map defining the sliding manifold

$$\mathcal{S}_m := \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n : s_m(x) = 0\}, \quad 0 \in \mathcal{S}_m.$$

Define $H_m(x, t) := \nabla s_m(x) g_m(x, t) \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$. The function s_m is admissible if $H_m(x, t)$ exists for all (x, t) and

$$\underline{\vartheta}_m \leq \sigma_{\min}(H_m(x, t)) \leq \sigma_{\max}(H_m(x, t)) \leq \bar{\vartheta}_m, \quad \forall x, t,$$

for some constants $0 < \underline{\vartheta}_m \leq \bar{\vartheta}_m < \infty$. Moreover, we require the bounds to hold uniformly over $m \in \mathcal{M}$, i.e., $\underline{\vartheta} := \inf_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \underline{\vartheta}_m > 0$, $\bar{\vartheta} := \sup_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \bar{\vartheta}_m < \infty$.

If $s_m(x) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ is chosen as in Definition 1, we pick a smooth map $z_m : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n-r}$ and define

$$T_m(x) := (s_m(x), z_m(x)) = (s, z). \quad (2)$$

Along a trajectory $x(\cdot)$ with mode signal $\sigma(\cdot)$ we write

$$(s(t), z(t)) := T_{\sigma(t)}(x(t)) = (s_{\sigma(t)}(x(t)), z_{\sigma(t)}(x(t))).$$

Assume that, for each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the Jacobian of T_m has full rank, so that T_m is a local diffeomorphism

with smooth inverse. In the coordinates (s, z) the system (1) can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{s}(t) &= f_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t) + g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t) u_{\sigma_i}(s, z, t), & (t, s, z) \notin \Gamma_i, \\ s(t^+) &= s(t^-) + J_{\sigma_{i+1}}^s(s(t^-), z(t^-)), & (t, s, z) \in \Gamma_i, \\ \dot{z}(t) &= f_{\sigma_i}^z(s, z, t) + g_{\sigma_i}^z(s, z, t) u_{\sigma_i}(s, z, t), & (t, s, z) \notin \Gamma_i, \\ z(t^+) &= z(t^-) + J_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(s(t^-), z(t^-)), & (t, s, z) \in \Gamma_i, \\ s(t_0^+) &\in \mathbb{R}^r, \quad z(t_0^+) \in \mathbb{R}^{n-r}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where, with a slight abuse of notation,

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_i &:= \{(t, s, z) \mid t = \theta_i + \tau_i(s, z)\}, \quad \tau_i(s, z) := \tau_i(T_{\sigma_i}^{-1}(s, z)) \\ u_{\sigma_i}(s, z, t) &:= u_{\sigma_i}(T_{\sigma_i}^{-1}(s, z), t). \end{aligned}$$

Here, J_m^s and J_m^z are induced by the state jump and the coordinate changes T_m .

The state is partitioned as $x = (s, z)$, where the s -subsystem Σ_s and the z -subsystem Σ_z denote the sliding and internal state dynamics, respectively. Although the state dimension n and the sliding dimension r may be mode-dependent, they are assumed constant across modes for notational simplicity.

In Section 3, a controller is designed to render Σ_s finite-time stable (in the sense of practical sliding). Section 5 then analyzes the stability of the internal dynamics Σ_z .

2.3. Assumptions on Dynamics

We impose the following standing assumptions on the continuous dynamics, jump maps, and uncertainties. These conditions hold for all modes $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and ensure well-posedness of trajectories and feasibility of controller design.

(A1) For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the functions $f_m^s : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^r$, $g_m^s : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{r \times r}$, $f_m^z : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n-r}$, $g_m^z : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{(n-r) \times r}$ are piecewise continuous in t and locally Lipschitz in (s, z) on compact subsets of $\mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r}$. We furthermore assume that $f_m^s(0, 0, t) = 0$ and $f_m^z(0, 0, t) = 0$ for all $t \geq t_0$ and all $m \in \mathcal{M}$.

(A2) The switching signal $\sigma : [t_0, \infty) \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ is piecewise constant and right-continuous. Let $\{\xi_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ denote the strictly increasing sequence of switching/impulse instants, with $t_0 < \xi_1 < \xi_2 < \dots$. Each event time satisfies $\xi_i = \theta_i + \tau_i(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))$, where $\{\theta_i\}_{i \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a strictly increasing nominal schedule and $\tau_i : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ is continuously differentiable. Equivalently, the i -th discontinuity surface is $\Gamma_i := \{(t, s, z) \mid t = \theta_i + \tau_i(s, z)\}$. The mode sequence is defined by $\sigma(t) = \sigma_i$ for $t \in [\xi_i, \xi_{i+1})$, $i \in \mathbb{N}$, and $\sigma(t) = \sigma_0$ for $t \in [t_0, \xi_1)$. Right-continuity implies $\sigma(\xi_i) = \sigma_i$ at each jump.

(A3) For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the jump maps $J_m^s : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^r$ and $J_m^z : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n-r}$ are locally Lipschitz in (s, z) . Moreover, their Lipschitz constants can be chosen uniformly over all modes $m \in \mathcal{M}$ on compact subsets of $\mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r}$. We also

assume that $J_m^z(0,0) = 0$ for all $m \in \mathcal{M}$. These jump maps account both for physical state resets and for additional (nonphysical) jumps induced by the coordinate transformation $x \mapsto (s, z)$.

(A4) For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the control law $u_m^c(s, z, t)$ is piecewise continuous in t and continuous in (s, z) . It is uniformly bounded as $\|u_m^c(s, z, t)\| \leq \bar{U}_m^c$, $\forall (s, z, t)$, for some constant $\bar{U}_m^c > 0$. Moreover, the mode-dependent bounds are uniformly bounded, i.e., $\bar{U}^c := \sup_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \bar{U}_m^c < \infty$.

(A5) For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the matched disturbance/uncertainty $d_m(s, z, t)$ is piecewise continuous in t , continuous in (s, z) , and uniformly bounded as $\|d_m(s, z, t)\| \leq \bar{D}_m$, $\forall (s, z, t)$, for some constant $\bar{D}_m > 0$.

For later use, define the total input in mode m as $u_m := u_m^c + d_m$ and its bound

$$\sup_{(s,z),t} \|u_m(s, z, t)\| \leq \bar{U}_m := \bar{U}_m^c + \bar{D}_m. \quad (4)$$

2.4. Assumptions on the Discontinuity Surfaces

State-dependent impulsive systems of the form (3) may exhibit the *beating phenomenon*, in which a trajectory intersects the same discontinuity surface $\Gamma_i := \{(t, s, z) : t = \theta_i + \tau_i(s, z)\}$ more than once within the window $[\theta_i, \theta_{i+1})$. Formally, beating occurs when $(t, s(t), z(t)) \in \Gamma_i$ at multiple distinct times inside this interval. To exclude beating, we impose Assumptions **(B1)**–**(B3)**, ensuring that each surface Γ_i is crossed *exactly once* by any solution, in accordance with the conditions established in [12, 13].

(B1) The nominal impulse schedule satisfies the uniform spacing bounds

$$0 < \underline{\theta} \leq \theta_{i+1} - \theta_i \leq \bar{\theta}, \quad \forall i \in \mathbb{N},$$

for some constants $\underline{\theta}, \bar{\theta} > 0$. The lower bound is assumed to satisfy $\underline{\theta} > \sup_i \bar{\tau}_i$, where $\bar{\tau}_i$ is an upper bound of $\tau_i(s, z)$, ensuring that each discontinuity surface Γ_i lies strictly inside its designated window $[\theta_i, \theta_{i+1})$.

(B2) Each state-dependent offset $\tau_i : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{>0}$ is continuous and satisfies the bounds

$$0 < \underline{\tau}_i \leq \tau_i(s, z) \leq \bar{\tau}_i, \quad \forall (s, z), \forall i \in \mathbb{N},$$

for some constants $\underline{\tau}_i, \bar{\tau}_i > 0$. Continuity implies that the sublevel set $\{(s, z) : \tau_i(s, z) < \bar{\tau}_i\}$ contains a neighborhood of the origin; hence there exists $R_i^- > 0$ such that

$$\|(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))\| \leq R_i^- \implies \tau_i(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-)) < \bar{\tau}_i.$$

Define the uniform lower and upper bounds $\underline{\tau} := \inf_i \underline{\tau}_i$, $\bar{\tau} := \sup_i \bar{\tau}_i$. A lower bound on the possible duration between two consecutive jumps, consistent with the bounds on τ_i and the nominal grid $\{\theta_i\}$, is then $T_{\min} := \underline{\theta} - \bar{\tau} + \underline{\tau}$.

(B3) For each i , define the event function $\psi_i(s, z, t) := t - \theta_i - \tau_i(s, z)$. For all trajectories $(s(t), z(t))$ with $t \in [\theta_i, \theta_i + \bar{\tau}_i)$ and at the jump time $t = \xi_i$, the condition

$$\dot{\psi}_i(s(t), z(t), t) (\psi_i(s_i^+, z_i^+, \xi_i) - \psi_i(s_i^-, z_i^-, \xi_i)) \geq \varrho_i > 0 \quad (5)$$

must hold for some constant $\varrho_i > 0$. Along solutions,

$$\dot{\psi}_i(s(t), z(t), t) = 1 - \left\langle \nabla \tau_i(s(t), z(t)), \begin{bmatrix} \dot{s}(t) \\ \dot{z}(t) \end{bmatrix} \right\rangle.$$

By Assumption **(B3)**, every trajectory intersects the surface Γ_i transversally and at most once (Thm. 5.3.1 in [12]). Figure 2 illustrates this mechanism: the blue trajectory, satisfying $\dot{\psi}_i > 0$, diverges from Γ_i after the initial intersection and thus avoids additional crossings, whereas the red trajectory, lacking monotonicity, repeatedly re-enters Γ_i and exhibits the beating phenomenon.

Figure 2: A sufficient condition under which the beating is prevented. A monotone $\psi(t)$ (blue) intersects the discontinuity surface, Γ_i , only once, whereas a non-monotone $\psi(t)$ (red) intersects it more than once.

Remark 1. Under Assumptions **(B1)**–**(B3)**, it can be shown that every solution of (1) intersects each discontinuity surface Γ_i , for all $i \in \mathbb{N}$, exactly once. For the detailed proof, see Lemma 5.3.2 and Theorem 5.3.1 in [12].

3. Sliding Manifold and Control Design

This section introduces a continuous reaching law for the system (3) and formalizes practical sliding. We derive mode-independent conditions on the minimum control input that ensure finite-time reachability of a prescribed tube $\|s(t)\| \leq \Delta^*$ for some mode m and invariance of this tube for all $m \in \mathcal{M}$. Using the regularity assumptions on the jump maps, we first establish a uniform affine upper bound on the post-jump sliding variable $\|s(\xi_i^+)\|$ in terms of the pre-jump state $(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))$, which is then used to select a suitable Δ^* .

3.1. Jumps in the sliding variable

At each impulse time ξ_i , a mode-dependent jump $(s^-, z^-) \mapsto (s^+, z^+)$ occurs through the map $J_{\sigma_i}^s, J_{\sigma_i}^z$. For the sliding analysis it is necessary to bound the

worst-case growth of the sliding variable across such jumps. The next lemma provides a uniform affine upper bound on $s(\xi_i^+)$ in terms of the pre-jump sliding variable $s(\xi_i^-)$, valid for all modes and all jump indices.

Lemma 1. *Let the jump maps J_m^s, J_m^z satisfy Assumption (A3) and let the no-beating conditions (B1)–(B3) hold. Then there exist constants $\alpha_s \geq 0$, $\beta_s \geq 0$, independent of i , such that for all jump times ξ_i ,*

$$\|s(\xi_i^+)\| \leq \alpha_s \|s(\xi_i^-)\| + \beta_s. \quad (6)$$

Proof. By Assumption (A3), each J_m^s is locally Lipschitz, so on the region reached before jumps there exist constants $L_{J_m^s}, \bar{J}_m^s \geq 0$ such that

$$\|J_m^s(s, z)\| \leq L_{J_m^s} (\|s\| + \|z\|) + \bar{J}_m^s.$$

Define $R^- := \sup_i R_i^- > 0$, where R_i^- is as in Assumption (B2). Then $\|(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))\| \leq R^-$ for all i . Hence, for the jump $\sigma(\xi_i^+) = \sigma_j$,

$$\begin{aligned} \|s(\xi_i^+)\| &= \|J_{\sigma_j}^s(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))\| \\ &\leq L_{J_{\sigma_j}^s} \|s(\xi_i^-)\| + L_{J_{\sigma_j}^s} R^- + \bar{J}_{\sigma_j}^s. \end{aligned}$$

Define

$$\alpha_s := \sup_{m \in \mathcal{M}} L_{J_m^s}, \quad \beta_s := \sup_{m \in \mathcal{M}} (L_{J_m^s} R^- + \bar{J}_m^s),$$

both finite on the compact region of interest. Then $\|s(\xi_i^+)\| \leq \alpha_s \|s(\xi_i^-)\| + \beta_s, \forall i$, which completes the proof. \square

Corollary 1. *Let $s_m(x) = C_m x$ with $C_m \in \mathbb{R}^{r \times n}$ of full row rank, and let the jump maps be linear, $x^+ = J_m x$ with $J_m \in \mathbb{R}^{n \times n}$. Assume there exists $R^- > 0$ such that $\|(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))\| \leq R^-, \forall i$. Let $P_m^\perp := I - C_m^\dagger C_m$ denote the orthogonal projector onto $\ker C_m$. Define $K_T := \sup_{\|(s, z)\| \leq R^-} \|T^{-1}(s, z)\| < \infty$, where T is the coordinate map in (2). Then the jump bound in Lemma 1 holds with*

$$\alpha_s = \sup_{m, \ell \in \mathcal{M}} \|C_\ell J_\ell C_m^\dagger\|, \quad \beta_s = K_T \sup_{m, \ell \in \mathcal{M}} \|C_\ell J_\ell P_m^\perp\|.$$

Proof. Fix a jump time ξ_i with pre-jump mode m and post-jump mode ℓ . Set $x^- := x(\xi_i^-)$ and $x^+ := x(\xi_i^+)$. By definition of K_T and the bound on $(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))$,

$$\|x^-\| = \|T^{-1}(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))\| \leq K_T.$$

Decompose

$$x^- = C_m^\dagger s_m(x^-) + P_m^\perp x^- = C_m^\dagger s^- + y,$$

where $y := P_m^\perp x^- \in \ker C_m$. So $\|y\| \leq \|x^-\| \leq K_T$. Using linearity of J_ℓ ,

$$s_\ell(x^+) = C_\ell J_\ell x^+ = C_\ell J_\ell C_m^\dagger s^- + C_\ell J_\ell y.$$

Taking norms,

$$\begin{aligned} \|s_\ell(x^+)\| &\leq \|C_\ell J_\ell C_m^\dagger\| \|s^-\| + \|C_\ell J_\ell P_m^\perp\| \|y\| \\ &\leq \alpha_s \|s^-\| + \beta_s, \end{aligned}$$

with α_s, β_s as defined above. \square

3.2. Reaching Law and Practical Sliding-Mode

This subsection introduces the notion of practical sliding for the mode-dependent manifolds \mathcal{S}_m and presents the continuous control law used to enforce it. We then establish conditions under which the proposed law guarantees finite-time reachability of the sliding tube \mathcal{T}_{Δ^*} despite jumps in the sliding variable and the presence of matched disturbances.

Definition 2. *Let $s(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ denote the sliding variable in the coordinates (s, z) of (3), and let $\Delta > 0$ be a prescribed desired boundary-layer radius. For a given tolerance $\Delta^* > 0$, the closed-loop system is said to achieve practical sliding if, for every initial condition $(s(t_0), z(t_0)) \in \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r}$, there exists a time $t_r \geq t_0$ such that:*

(i) *Reachability:* There holds $\|s(t_r)\| < \Delta$.

(ii) *Tube invariance:* For all $t \geq t_r$, $\|s(t)\| \leq \Delta^*$.

We now design a control input that induces practical sliding on the mode-dependent manifolds \mathcal{S}_m as in Definition 2. The control input in mode m is decomposed as

$$u_m^c(s, z, t) = u_m^{\text{eq}}(s, z, t) + u_m^n(s, z, t), \quad (7)$$

where u_m^{eq} renders the nominal dynamics tangent to \mathcal{S}_m , and u_m^n enforces reachability and tube invariance.

Equivalent control. For a fixed mode m , the s -dynamics of (3) can be written as

$$\dot{s} = f_m^s(s, z, t) + g_m^s(s, z, t) u_m^c(s, z, t) + g_m^s(s, z, t) d_m(s, z, t),$$

where we have separated the control input u_m^c and the matched disturbance d_m . The equivalent control is defined by imposing $\dot{s} = 0$ for the nominal dynamics on the sliding manifold, i.e. for $s = 0$ and $d_m \equiv 0$:

$$f_m^s(0, z, t) + g_m^s(0, z, t) u_m^{\text{eq}}(0, z, t) = 0.$$

Definition 1 guarantees that $g_m^s(0, z, t)$ is uniformly nonsingular on \mathcal{S}_m , yielding

$$u_m^{\text{eq}}(0, z, t) = -(g_m^s(0, z, t))^{-1} f_m^s(0, z, t). \quad (8)$$

Correction control. To drive $s(t)$ into the tube $\mathcal{T}_\Delta := \{(s, z) : \|s\| \leq \Delta\}$ and maintain \mathcal{T}_{Δ^*} despite matched disturbances and hybrid jumps, we employ the finite-time boundary-layer control

$$u_m^n(s, z, t) = -\kappa_s (g_m^s(s, z, t))^{-1} \|s\|^p \text{sat}(s/\Delta), \quad (9)$$

where $0 < p < 1$, $\kappa_s > 0$, and

$$\text{sat}(y) = \begin{cases} y, & \|y\| \leq 1, \\ y/\|y\|, & \|y\| > 1. \end{cases}$$

The radius $\Delta > 0$ defines the *desired* boundary layer; the correction term ensures reachability of \mathcal{T}_Δ and provides robustness against bounded matched disturbances and jumps of the sliding variable.

Remark 2. Note that $u_m^n(0,0,t) = 0$ and, by Assumption **(A1)**, $u_m^{\text{eq}}(0,0,t) = 0$. Moreover, Assumption **(A1)** implies $f_m^z(0,0,t) = 0$, and Assumption **(A3)** gives $J_m^z(0,0) = 0$. Hence, $(s,z) = (0,0)$ is an equilibrium of Σ_z (i.e., it is invariant under both the flow and jump dynamics).

Assume that there exist $R^z > 0$ and a finite bound

$$\bar{U}^{\text{eq}} := \sup_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \sup_{\|z\| \leq R^z, t \geq t_0} \|u_m^{\text{eq}}(z,t)\| < \infty$$

such that $\|z(t)\| \leq R^z$ along the closed-loop trajectories. Define the guaranteed correction margin $\underline{U}^n := \bar{U}^c - \bar{U}^{\text{eq}} > 0$, where \bar{U}^c is the uniform upper bound on the available control input from Assumption **(A4)**.

The next theorem provides sufficient conditions on the correction margin \underline{U}^n and the reaching gain κ_s under which the control law (7) enforces practical sliding for the system (3).

Theorem 1. Consider the state-dependent impulsive switched system (3) under Assumptions **(A1)**–**(A5)** and **(B1)**–**(B3)**, and let the sliding variables s_m be admissible in the sense of Definition 1. Let $u_m^c = u_m^{\text{eq}} + u_m^n$ be the control law (7), where u_m^{eq} is given by (8) and u_m^n by (9) with parameters (κ_s, Δ, p) , $0 < p < 1$.

Set

$$\underline{\vartheta} := \inf_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \underline{\vartheta}_m, \quad \Phi^{\max} := \sup_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \bar{\vartheta}_m \bar{D}_m,$$

where $\underline{\vartheta}_m$ and $\bar{\vartheta}_m$ are the singular-value bounds from Definition 1, and \bar{D}_m is the disturbance bound from Assumption **(A5)**. Let α_s and β_s be the jump constants obtained in Lemma 1, and let T_{\min} be the minimum inter-jump time from Assumption **(B2)**.

Suppose that the available correction margin satisfies

$$\underline{U}^n \geq \max \left\{ \frac{\Phi^{\max}}{\underline{\vartheta}}, \frac{T_{\min} \Phi^{\max} + (\alpha_s - 1)\Delta + \beta_s}{T_{\min} \underline{\vartheta}} \right\}, \quad (10)$$

and that the hardware bound is large enough to realize this margin, i.e. $\bar{U}^c \geq \bar{U}^{\text{eq}} + \underline{U}^n$.

Choose the reaching gain κ_s so that, for $\bar{\vartheta} := \sup_m \bar{\vartheta}_m$,

$$\kappa_s \geq \frac{\underline{U}^n \bar{\vartheta}}{\Delta^p}. \quad (11)$$

Assume furthermore that there exists an index i^* such that the inter-jump interval satisfies

$$\xi_{i^*+1} - \xi_{i^*} \geq \frac{\|s(\xi_{i^*}^+)\| - \Delta}{\lambda_s}, \quad (12)$$

where $\lambda_s := \underline{\vartheta} \underline{U}^n - \Phi^{\max} > 0$.

Then every closed-loop trajectory of (3) satisfies:

1. Finite-time reachability: There exists $t_r < \infty$ such that $\|s(t_r)\| < \Delta$.

2. Tube invariance despite impulses: For all $t \geq t_r$, $\|s(t)\| \leq \Delta^*$, $\Delta^* := \alpha_s \Delta + \beta_s$.

Hence the closed-loop impulsive switched system achieves practical sliding of width Δ^* on every sliding manifold \mathcal{S}_m .

Proof. Fix an interval $t \in [\xi_i, \xi_{i+1})$ and let $s(t) \in \mathbb{R}^r$ denote the sliding variable. From (3) and the decomposition $u_{\sigma_i}^c = u_{\sigma_i}^{\text{eq}} + u_{\sigma_i}^n$ we have, along flows,

$$\dot{s} = f_{\sigma_i}^s + g_{\sigma_i}^s (u_{\sigma_i}^{\text{eq}} + u_{\sigma_i}^n + d_{\sigma_i}).$$

By definition of the equivalent control $u_{\sigma_i}^{\text{eq}}$ in (8), the nominal s -dynamics on the manifold satisfy $f_{\sigma_i}^s + g_{\sigma_i}^s u_{\sigma_i}^{\text{eq}} = 0$, hence

$$\dot{s} = g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t) u_{\sigma_i}^n(s, z, t) + g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t) d_{\sigma_i}(s, z, t). \quad (13)$$

For $\|s\| > \Delta$ the saturation satisfies $\text{sat}(s/\Delta) = s/\|s\|$, so from (9),

$$u_{\sigma_i}^n = -\kappa_s (g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t))^{-1} \|s\|^p \frac{s}{\|s\|}.$$

Definition 1 guarantees that $g_{\sigma_i}^s$ is uniformly nonsingular, with singular values bounded as $\sigma_{\min}(g_{\sigma_i}^s) \geq \underline{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i}$ and $\sigma_{\max}(g_{\sigma_i}^s) \leq \bar{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i}$. In particular, for any unit vector v , $\|(g_{\sigma_i}^s)^{-1}v\| \geq 1/\bar{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i}$. Therefore, for $\|s\| \geq \Delta$,

$$\|u_{\sigma_i}^n\| = \kappa_s \|s\|^p \left\| (g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t))^{-1} \frac{s}{\|s\|} \right\| \geq \frac{\kappa_s \Delta^p}{\bar{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i}}.$$

By the choice of κ_s in (11), $\kappa_s \Delta^p / \bar{\vartheta} \geq \underline{U}^n$, and since $\bar{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i} \leq \bar{\vartheta}$ we obtain $\|u_{\sigma_i}^n\| \geq \underline{U}^n$ whenever $\|s\| > \Delta$. By design, the correction input is saturated at magnitude \underline{U}^n (and the actuator bound $\bar{U}^c \geq \bar{U}^{\text{eq}} + \underline{U}^n$ guarantees this is implementable), so for $\|s\| > \Delta$,

$$u_{\sigma_i}^n = -\underline{U}^n \frac{(g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t))^{-1} \text{sat}(s/\Delta)}{\left\| (g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t))^{-1} \text{sat}(s/\Delta) \right\|}.$$

Substituting this expression into (13) and using $\|g_{\sigma_i}^s(s, z, t) d_{\sigma_i}(s, z, t)\| \leq \bar{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i} \bar{D}_{\sigma_i}$ yields, for $\|s\| > 0$,

$$\|\dot{s}\| = \frac{s^\top}{\|s\|} \dot{s} \leq -\underline{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i} \underline{U}^n + \bar{\vartheta}_{\sigma_i} \bar{D}_{\sigma_i} \leq -\lambda_s, \quad (14)$$

where $\lambda_s := \underline{\vartheta} \underline{U}^n - \Phi^{\max} > 0$. Hence, for $\|s\| > \Delta$ and $t \in [\xi_i, \xi_{i+1})$,

$$\|s(t)\| \leq [\|s(\xi_i^+)\| - \lambda_s(t - \xi_i)]_+. \quad (15)$$

(1) *Finite-time reachability of $\|s\| < \Delta$.* For an interval $[\xi_{i^*}, \xi_{i^*+1})$ satisfying (12), (15) gives the crossing time

$$t_r := \xi_{i^*} + \frac{\|s(\xi_{i^*}^+)\| - \Delta}{\lambda_s} \leq \xi_{i^*+1},$$

so $\|s(t_r)\| < \Delta$. Thus the tube $\mathcal{T}_\Delta := \{(s, z) : \|s\| \leq \Delta\}$ is entered in finite time.

(2) *Invariance during flows.* On the boundary $\|s\| = \Delta$, inequality (14) gives $\|s\| \leq -\lambda_s < 0$, so the boundary $\|s\| = \Delta$ is strictly inward pointing and therefore forward invariant under flows as long as $\|s\| \geq \Delta$.

(3) *Effect of jumps.* Lemma 1 shows that each jump satisfies $\|s(\xi_i^+)\| \leq \alpha_s \|s(\xi_i^-)\| + \beta_s$. Thus, whenever $\|s(\xi_i^-)\| \leq \Delta$, the post-jump value satisfies $\|s(\xi_i^+)\| \leq \alpha_s \Delta + \beta_s$. To prevent accumulation across impulses, $\|s\|$ must return from $\alpha_s \Delta + \beta_s$ down to Δ before the next jump. Using (15) over the minimal inter-jump interval T_{\min} gives the requirement

$$\Delta \leq (\alpha_s \Delta + \beta_s) - \lambda_s T_{\min},$$

which is equivalent to the lower bound on \underline{U}^n in (10). Under this bound, each continuous-flow segment compensates the maximal possible jump in s .

(4) *Practical sliding.* Steps 1–3 imply that there exists a finite t_r such that $\|s(t_r)\| < \Delta$, and for all $t \geq t_r$ and all subsequent jumps one has $\|s(\xi_i^+)\| \leq \alpha_s \Delta + \beta_s$. Hence the forward-invariant tube

$$\mathcal{T}_{\Delta^*} := \{(s, z) : \|s\| \leq \Delta^*\}, \quad \Delta^* := \alpha_s \Delta + \beta_s,$$

is reached in finite time and never exited under either flows or jumps. This is precisely practical sliding in the sense of Definition 2. \square

Remark 3. *Before entering the tube \mathcal{T}_{Δ} , the evolution of $\|s(t)\|$ is governed by the continuous-flow decay (15) and the jump bound (6). By repeatedly composing these two relations across successive intervals $[\xi_i, \xi_{i+1})$, one obtains an explicit global upper bound on $\|s(t)\|$ in terms of $\|s_{\sigma_0}(t_0)\|$ and the parameters $(\alpha_s, \beta_s, \lambda_s, T_{\min})$. This yields a conservative closed-form estimate of the reaching time t_r . For brevity, the explicit expression is omitted here.*

Remark 4. *The idea of forcing the trajectory to re-enter a prescribed tube within a given time before the next jump, so as to prevent accumulation of jumps and divergence of a variable, also appears in the design of funnel controllers for time-dependent impulsive switched systems, see [20, 21].*

Having established in Theorem 1 that the control law (7) renders the s -dynamics practically sliding, there exists $t_r \geq t_0$ such that the sliding variable remains confined to the tube $\mathcal{T}_{\Delta^*} := \{(s, z) : \|s\| \leq \Delta^*\}$ for all $t \geq t_r$. To assess the stability of the full system (3), it remains to study the internal dynamics z under this practically sliding regime.

In the next section we introduce a comparison system, called the B -equivalent system, which converts the state-dependent switching in the z -dynamics into an equivalent time-dependent description. This representation allows us to establish dwell-time conditions under which the nominal internal dynamics are exponentially stable.

4. B-Equivalent System Formulation

To analyze stability of the internal dynamics z in (3), it is convenient to eliminate the *state-dependent* jump times ξ_i . We do so via the B -equivalent transformation [12], which replaces the trajectory-dependent jump instants ξ_i by the fixed anchor sequence $\{\theta_i\}$. This yields a time-scheduled impulsive system that admits standard hybrid Lyapunov and dwell-time analysis tools.

The following subsections summarize this transformation and establish that stability of the time-dependent B -equivalent system transfers directly to the original state-dependent dynamics.

4.1. From State- to Time-Dependent Jumps

We employ the B -equivalent transformation [12], which replaces the state-dependent jump times $\xi_i = \theta_i + \tau_i(x(\xi_i^-))$ with the fixed anchor sequence $\{\theta_i\}$, while ensuring that the resulting trajectory coincides with the original solution at each true jump instant ξ_i .

The B -equivalent time-dependent impulsive system for the internal dynamics, denoted by $\hat{\Sigma}_z$, is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{z}}(t) &= f_{\sigma_i}^z(s(t), \hat{z}(t), t) + g_{\sigma_i}^z(s(t), \hat{z}(t), t) u_{\sigma_i}(s(t), \hat{z}(t), t), & t \in [\theta_i, \theta_{i+1}), \\ \hat{z}(t^+) &= W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(s(t^-), \hat{z}(t^-)), & t = \theta_i, \\ \hat{z}(t_0^+) &= z(t_0^+), & \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

where $W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z : \mathbb{R}^r \times \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^{n-r}$ is a nonlinear map to be specified below. The signal $s(t)$ is the sliding variable generated by the closed-loop s -dynamics and is treated here as a given (exogenous but bounded) input.

This transformation guarantees that, for each solution $(s(t), z(t))$ of the original state-dependent system (3), there exists a corresponding solution $\hat{z}(t)$ of (16) such that $\hat{z}(t) = z(t)$, $t \in [\xi_i, \theta_{i+1})$, and

$$\hat{z}(\xi_i) = z(\xi_i^+), \quad \hat{z}(\theta_i^+) = W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(s(\theta_i), z(\theta_i)), \quad \forall i \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Thus, the original state-dependent jump at ξ_i is captured by performing a jump at θ_i in the transformed system and then flowing forward to ξ_i , where the two trajectories coincide again. The conceptual idea is depicted in Fig. 1.

To construct $W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z$, we impose the consistency conditions

$$\hat{z}(\theta_i^-) = z(\theta_i^-) = z(\theta_i), \quad \hat{z}(\xi_i^-) = \hat{z}(\xi_i^+) = z(\xi_i^+).$$

For each mode m , let $\Phi_m^z(t, t_0, z_0)$ denote the nonlinear flow of the internal dynamics $\dot{z} = f_m^z(s(t), z, t) + g_m^z(s(t), z, t) u_m(s(t), z, t)$, $z(t_0) = z_0$, induced by the given input signals $s(\cdot)$ and $u_m(\cdot)$. Between anchor times θ_i and θ_{i+1} , with intermediate jump time ξ_i , the original system satisfies

$$z(\xi_i^-) = \Phi_{\sigma_i}^z(\xi_i, \theta_i, z(\theta_i)), \quad z(\xi_i^+) = J_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-)),$$

while the B-equivalent internal system must satisfy

$$\hat{z}(\theta_i^+) = \Phi_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(\theta_i, \xi_i, z(\xi_i^+)).$$

Combining the above gives the explicit B-jump map

$$W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(s(\theta_i), z) := \Phi_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z\left(\theta_i, \xi_i, J_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(s(\xi_i^-), \Phi_{\sigma_i}^z(\xi_i, \theta_i, z))\right), \quad (17)$$

where $\xi_i = \theta_i + \tau_i(s(\xi_i^-), z(\xi_i^-))$ is the corresponding state-dependent event time. For brevity we write $W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(z)$ when the dependence on the (bounded) input signals $s(\cdot)$ and $u(\cdot)$ is clear from the context.

Remark 5. *In the B-equivalent formulation, the map W_m^z is a purely theoretical construct: it is never computed in practice and plays no role in the controller implementation. Its existence, ensured under the standing regularity and transversality assumptions (see [12, Ch. 5]; cf. [22, 23]), is sufficient for the stability analysis and extends verbatim to general state-dependent impulsive systems with bounded inputs.*

4.2. Stability Transfer to the Original System

This subsection shows that global exponential stability of the *nominal* time-dependent internal dynamics $\hat{\Sigma}_z$ implies a practical exponential stability property for the internal dynamics Σ_z of the original state-dependent system.

The argument proceeds in two steps. First, we derive a uniform growth bound for trajectories of Σ_z on any jump-free interval under bounded inputs generated by the practically sliding s -dynamics and the matched disturbance. Then, we show that if the nominal B-equivalent dynamics $\hat{\Sigma}_z$ (with $u^c = u^{\text{eq}}$, $s \equiv 0$, and no disturbance) are globally exponentially stable, then trajectories of Σ_z remain uniformly close to the origin, with an ultimate bound depending on the sliding tube radius and disturbance level.

Lemma 2. *Consider any jump-free interval $[t_a, t_b]$ contained in a single mode σ_i , i.e., $\xi_i < t_a < t_b \leq \xi_{i+1}$, with $t_a \geq t_r$ so that $\|s(t)\| \leq \Delta^*$ for all $t \in [t_a, t_b]$. Let $\Delta t := t_b - t_a > 0$. Then every solution of the z -dynamics in (3) with input satisfying Assumptions (A4)–(A5) obeys*

$$\|z(t_b^-)\| \leq C_{\sigma_i}^1(\Delta t) \|z(t_a)\| + C_{\sigma_i}^2(\Delta t), \quad (18)$$

for some continuous functions $C_{\sigma_i}^1, C_{\sigma_i}^2 : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$, depending on the mode σ_i , the bounds on s and on the input.

Proof. On $[t_a, t_b]$ the mode is fixed at σ_i and, by practical sliding, $\|s(t)\| \leq \Delta^*$ for all $t \in [t_a, t_b]$. By Assumption (A1) there exist constants $L_{f_{\sigma_i}^z}, L_{g_{\sigma_i}^z}, \bar{g}_{\sigma_i}^z \geq 0$ such that for all (s, z) in the compact region visited by the trajectory,

$$\|f_{\sigma_i}^z(s, z, t)\| \leq L_{f_{\sigma_i}^z} \|s, z\|, \|g_{\sigma_i}^z(s, z, t)\| \leq L_{g_{\sigma_i}^z} \|s, z\| + \bar{g}_{\sigma_i}^z.$$

Using the input bound $\|u_{\sigma_i}(s, z, t)\| \leq \bar{U}_{\sigma_i}$ we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \|\dot{z}(t)\| &\leq \|f_{\sigma_i}^z(s, z, t)\| + \|g_{\sigma_i}^z(s, z, t)\| \|u_{\sigma_i}(s, z, t)\| \\ &\leq L_{f_{\sigma_i}^z} (\|z(t)\| + \Delta^*) + (L_{g_{\sigma_i}^z} (\|z(t)\| + \Delta^*) + \bar{g}_{\sigma_i}^z) \bar{U}_{\sigma_i}. \end{aligned}$$

Define

$$C_{\sigma_i}^0 := L_{f_{\sigma_i}^z} + L_{g_{\sigma_i}^z} \bar{U}_{\sigma_i}, \quad B_{\sigma_i} := (L_{f_{\sigma_i}^z} + L_{g_{\sigma_i}^z} \bar{U}_{\sigma_i}) \Delta^* + \bar{g}_{\sigma_i}^z \bar{U}_{\sigma_i}.$$

Then $\|\dot{z}(t)\| \leq C_{\sigma_i}^0 \|z(t)\| + B_{\sigma_i}$. Let $r(t) := \|z(t)\|$. We have $\dot{r}(t) \leq C_{\sigma_i}^0 r(t) + B_{\sigma_i}$, $t \in [t_a, t_b]$. Applying Grönwall on $[t_a, t_b]$ yields

$$r(t_b^-) \leq e^{C_{\sigma_i}^0 \Delta t} r(t_a) + \frac{e^{C_{\sigma_i}^0 \Delta t} - 1}{C_{\sigma_i}^0} B_{\sigma_i},$$

with the second term interpreted as $\Delta t B_{\sigma_i}$ when $C_{\sigma_i}^0 = 0$. Since $r(t) = \|z(t)\|$, (18) holds with

$$C_{\sigma_i}^1(\Delta t) := e^{C_{\sigma_i}^0 \Delta t}, \quad C_{\sigma_i}^2(\Delta t) := \begin{cases} \frac{e^{C_{\sigma_i}^0 \Delta t} - 1}{C_{\sigma_i}^0} B_{\sigma_i}, & C_{\sigma_i}^0 > 0, \\ \Delta t B_{\sigma_i}, & C_{\sigma_i}^0 = 0. \end{cases}$$

This completes the proof. \square

The next proposition establishes the main result of this subsection: if the nominal time-dependent internal dynamics $\hat{\Sigma}_z$ are exponentially stable, then the original state-dependent internal dynamics Σ_z are practically exponentially stable. Here “nominal” refers to the B-equivalent internal system with $u^c = u^{\text{eq}}$, $s \equiv 0$, and zero disturbance, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{z}}(t) &= f_{\sigma_i}^{z, \text{eq}}(\hat{z}, t) := f_{\sigma_i}^z(0, \hat{z}, t) + g_{\sigma_i}^z(0, \hat{z}, t) u_{\sigma_i}^{\text{eq}}(0, \hat{z}, t), \\ &\quad t \in [\theta_i, \theta_{i+1}), \\ \hat{z}(t^+) &= W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^{z, \text{eq}}(\hat{z}) := W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^z(0, \hat{z}), \quad t = \theta_i, \\ \hat{z}(t_0^+) &= z(t_0^+). \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

Proposition 1. *Consider the internal dynamics Σ_z in (3) and its time-dependent B-equivalent system $\hat{\Sigma}_z$ in (16), with inputs satisfying Assumptions (A4)–(A5). Assume that:*

- the standing regularity and transversality assumptions (A1)–(A5) and (B1)–(B3) hold;*
- the nominal B-equivalent internal system (19) is globally exponentially stable, i.e., there exist $c, \alpha > 0$ such that*

$$\|\hat{z}(t)\| \leq c e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} \|\hat{z}(t_0)\|, \quad \forall t \geq t_0;$$

- practical sliding has been established for Σ_s with tube $\|s(t)\| \leq \Delta^*$ for all $t \geq t_r$, as in Theorem 1.*

Then the internal dynamics Σ_z are globally practically exponentially stable: there exist constants $\tilde{c}, \tilde{b}, \tilde{d} > 0$ such that every solution $z(t)$ of Σ_z satisfies

$$\|z(t)\| \leq \tilde{c} e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} \|z(t_0)\| + \tilde{b} \Delta^* + \tilde{d}, \quad \forall t \geq t_0. \quad (20)$$

In particular, if $\Delta^ = 0$ and the matched disturbance is zero, then Σ_z is globally exponentially stable.*

Proof. By construction of the B-equivalent internal system,

$$z(\theta_i) = \hat{z}(\theta_i^-), \quad \forall i \in \mathbb{N}.$$

By assumption (b), $\hat{\Sigma}_z$ is globally exponentially stable, hence evaluating at $t = \theta_i$ gives

$$\|z(\theta_i)\| = \|\hat{z}(\theta_i^-)\| \leq c e^{-\alpha(\theta_i - t_0)} \|z(t_0)\|. \quad (21)$$

For $t \geq t_r$ practical sliding yields $\|s(t)\| \leq \Delta^*$, and the total input to Σ_z (equivalent control, correction term, and disturbance) is uniformly bounded by Assumptions **(A4)**–**(A5)**. Lemma 2 applied on each interval $[\theta_i, t) \subset [\theta_i, \xi_i)$ then yields

$$\|z(t)\| \leq C_{\sigma_i}^1(t - \theta_i) \|z(\theta_i)\| + C_{\sigma_i}^2(t - \theta_i),$$

with $C_{\sigma_i}^1, C_{\sigma_i}^2$ depending only on the mode, Δ^* , and the input bounds. By Assumption **(B1)**, $t - \theta_i \leq \bar{\theta}$, so there exist uniform constants $\bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 > 0$ such that

$$\|z(t)\| \leq \bar{C}_1 \|z(\theta_i)\| + \bar{C}_2, \quad t \in [\theta_i, \xi_i).$$

Combining this with (21) and using $\theta_i \leq t$ gives

$$\begin{aligned} \|z(t)\| &\leq \bar{C}_1 c e^{-\alpha(\theta_i - t_0)} \|z(t_0)\| + \bar{C}_2 \\ &\leq \tilde{c} e^{-\alpha(t - t_0)} \|z(t_0)\| + \tilde{b} \Delta^* + \tilde{d}, \end{aligned}$$

for suitable $\tilde{c}, \tilde{b}, \tilde{d} > 0$ that absorb \bar{C}_1, \bar{C}_2 and the dependence on the disturbance bounds. If $\Delta^* = 0$ and the disturbance is zero, then $s(t) \equiv 0$ for $t \geq t_r$. Hence $u^n \equiv 0$, and by $f_m^z(0, 0, t) = 0$ and the definition of u^{eq} we also have $u^{\text{eq}}(0, 0, t) = 0$. In this case the forcing term in Lemma 2 vanishes, so the additive term in (20) is zero and we recover global exponential stability of Σ_z .

This proves (20). \square

5. Stability of the Nominal Internal Dynamics

By Proposition 1, global exponential stability of the nominal B-equivalent internal system $\hat{\Sigma}_z$ is a sufficient condition for global practical exponential stability of the original state-dependent internal dynamics Σ_z , provided practical sliding has been achieved.

In this section we therefore analyze stability of the nominal B-equivalent system. First, we derive mode-dependent average dwell-time conditions that guarantee global exponential stability (GES) of the nominal internal dynamics (19). Next, we specialize to a case in which the nominal subsystem admits a convex polytopic representation of affine dynamics; for this class, we formulate LMI conditions ensuring GES. Finally, we present a search procedure for sliding manifolds of the form $s_m(x) = C_m x$ that simultaneously enforce GES of the nominal B-equivalent dynamics and guarantee the absence of beating.

5.1. Stability Under Weighted Mode-Dependent Average Dwell Time

Consider the nominal B-equivalent system (19). Our goal in this subsection is to derive sufficient conditions ensuring global exponential stability of this system. The key technical tool is a mode-dependent average dwell-time condition, which generalizes the classical ADT requirement to hybrid systems whose continuous dynamics and jump maps are both mode dependent and nonlinear.

For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$ define

$$T_m(t_0, t) := \text{meas}\{\tau \in [t_0, t) : \sigma(\tau) = m\},$$

the total (continuous) time spent in mode m on $[t_0, t)$, and

$$N_m(t_0, t) := \#\{i : \theta_i \in [t_0, t), \sigma_i = m\},$$

the number of entries into mode m over $[t_0, t)$, where meas denotes Lebesgue measure and $\#$ denotes cardinality.

Definition 3. *The switching signal $\sigma(\cdot)$ is said to satisfy a mode-dependent average dwell-time condition if for each $m \in \mathcal{M}$ there exist constants $N_{0,m} \geq 0$ and $\tau_{a,m} > 0$ such that*

$$N_m(t_0, t) \leq N_{0,m} + \frac{T_m(t_0, t)}{\tau_{a,m}}, \quad \forall t \geq t_0. \quad (22)$$

We next introduce a mode-dependent Lyapunov framework and derive a sufficient condition for uniform exponential contraction of the nominal B-equivalent system under this weighted ADT (wADT) constraint.

Remark 6. *In the stability analysis, we treat $f_m^{z,\text{eq}}(\hat{z}, t)$ in (19) as a generic nonlinear vector field. All results below apply to any system of the form $\dot{x} = F(x, t)$ satisfying the stated assumptions.*

Theorem 2. *Consider the impulsive switched system (19). Let $\mathcal{M} = \{1, \dots, M\}$ be the set of modes, and let $\sigma : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathcal{M}$ be a right-continuous, piecewise-constant switching signal with switching times $0 \leq t_0 < \theta_1 < \theta_2 < \dots$ (with $\theta_0 := t_0$). For each $m \in \mathcal{M}$, let*

$$V_m : \mathbb{R}^{n-r} \times \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$$

be continuously differentiable, positive-definite functions, and let $\mu_m \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\eta_{j,i} > 0$ be constants such that:

1. *For all $t \in [\theta_i, \theta_{i+1})$,*

$$\dot{V}_{\sigma_i}(\hat{z}(t), t) \leq \mu_{\sigma_i} V_{\sigma_i}(\hat{z}(t), t). \quad (23)$$

2. *At each switching time θ_i ,*

$$V_{\sigma_{i+1}}(\hat{z}(\theta_i^+), \theta_i) \leq \eta_{i+1,i} V_{\sigma_i}(\hat{z}(\theta_i^-), \theta_i). \quad (24)$$

Assume the mode-dependent ADT condition (22) holds for all modes m , and define for each $m \in \mathcal{M}$ the combined dissipation rate

$$\lambda_m := \mu_m + \frac{\ln(\eta_m)}{\tau_{a,m}}, \quad \eta_m := \max_i \eta_{m,i}, \quad (25)$$

where $\tau_{a,m} > 0$ is the average dwell time for mode m . Fix $0 < \epsilon < \delta$ and partition \mathcal{M} into

$$\mathcal{M}_S := \{m : \lambda_m \leq -\delta\}, \quad \mathcal{M}_M := \{m : -\delta < \lambda_m < \epsilon\}, \\ \mathcal{M}_U := \{m : \lambda_m \geq \epsilon\},$$

and let $\lambda_U^{\max} = \max_{m \in \mathcal{M}_U} \lambda_m$. For $t \geq t_0$, define

$$T_S = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_S} T_m, \quad T_U = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_U} T_m,$$

where $T_m(t_0, t)$ is the cumulative time spent in mode m on $[t_0, t)$.

Assume there exist $\gamma \geq 0$ and $\rho > \lambda_U^{\max}/\delta$ such that

$$T_U + \frac{\epsilon}{\lambda_U^{\max}} \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_M} \omega_m T_m \leq \gamma + \frac{1}{\rho} T_S, \quad \forall t \geq t_0, \quad (26)$$

where

$$\omega_m := \frac{\lambda_m + \delta}{\epsilon + \delta} \in (0, 1).$$

Suppose moreover that there exist class- \mathcal{K} functions $\underline{v}, \bar{v} : \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_{\geq 0}$ such that, for every solution $\hat{z}(t)$,

$$\underline{v}(\|\hat{z}(t)\|) \leq V_{\sigma(t)}(\hat{z}(t), t) \leq \bar{v}(\|\hat{z}(t)\|). \quad (27)$$

Then for every solution $\hat{z}(t)$ of (19) with initial condition $\hat{z}(t_0) = \hat{z}_0$, there exist constants $c \geq 1$ and $\alpha > 0$ such that

$$\|\hat{z}(t)\| \leq c e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} \|\hat{z}_0\|, \quad \forall t \geq t_0, \quad (28)$$

i.e., the system is uniformly globally exponentially stable.

Proof. Integrating (23) on each dwell interval $[\theta_i, \theta_{i+1})$ where mode σ_i is active gives

$$V_{\sigma_i}(\hat{z}(\theta_{i+1}^-), \theta_{i+1}) \leq e^{\mu_{\sigma_i}(\theta_{i+1}-\theta_i)} V_{\sigma_i}(\hat{z}(\theta_i^+), \theta_i).$$

Combining with (24) yields, for each i ,

$$V_{\sigma_i}(\hat{z}(\theta_{i+1}^-), \theta_{i+1}) \leq \eta_{i,i-1} e^{\mu_{\sigma_i}(\theta_{i+1}-\theta_i)} V_{\sigma_{i-1}}(\hat{z}(\theta_i^-), \theta_i).$$

Iterating from t_0 to $t \in [\theta_i, \theta_{i+1})$ and collecting factors mode-wise gives

$$V_{\sigma(t)}(\hat{z}(t), t) \leq \prod_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \eta_m^{N_m(t_0, t)} e^{\mu_m T_m(t_0, t)} V_{\sigma_0}(\hat{z}_0, t_0),$$

where $N_m(t_0, t)$ is the number of entries into mode m on $[t_0, t)$. Taking logarithms,

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \frac{V_{\sigma(t)}(\hat{z}(t), t)}{V_{\sigma_0}(\hat{z}_0, t_0)} &\leq \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} N_m(t_0, t) \ln(\eta_m) + \mu_m T_m(t_0, t) \\ &\leq \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \left(N_{0,m} + \frac{T_m(t_0, t)}{\tau_{a,m}} \right) \ln(\eta_m) + \mu_m T_m(t_0, t) \\ &= K + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \left(\mu_m + \frac{\ln(\eta_m)}{\tau_{a,m}} \right) T_m(t_0, t) \\ &= K + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \lambda_m T_m(t_0, t), \end{aligned}$$

where $K := \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} N_{0,m} \ln(\eta_m)$. Splitting the sum over $\mathcal{M}_S, \mathcal{M}_M, \mathcal{M}_U$ and using the definitions of ω_m and λ_U^{\max} gives

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \frac{V_{\sigma(t)}(\hat{z}(t), t)}{V_{\sigma_0}(\hat{z}_0, t_0)} &\leq K + \lambda_U^{\max} T_U - \delta T_S \\ &\quad + \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}_M} [-\delta(1 - \omega_m) + \epsilon \omega_m] T_m. \end{aligned}$$

Applying the weighted ADT constraint (26) yields

$$\begin{aligned} \ln \frac{V_{\sigma(t)}(\hat{z}(t), t)}{V_{\sigma_0}(\hat{z}_0, t_0)} &\leq K + \lambda_U^{\max} \gamma - \left(\delta - \frac{\lambda_U^{\max}}{\rho} \right) T_S(t_0, t) \\ &\leq K + \lambda_U^{\max} \gamma - \left(\delta - \frac{\lambda_U^{\max}}{\rho} \right) (t - t_0), \end{aligned}$$

since $T_S(t_0, t) \geq t - t_0$. Let $c_V := \exp(K + \lambda_U^{\max} \gamma)$ and $\alpha := \delta - \lambda_U^{\max}/\rho > 0$. Then

$$V_{\sigma(t)}(\hat{z}(t), t) \leq c_V e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} V_{\sigma_0}(\hat{z}_0, t_0), \quad t \geq t_0.$$

Using the comparison bound (27),

$$\underline{v}(\|\hat{z}(t)\|) \leq c_V e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} \bar{v}(\|\hat{z}_0\|).$$

Since \underline{v}, \bar{v} are class- \mathcal{K} , there exists $c \geq 1$ such that

$$\|\hat{z}(t)\| \leq c e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} \|\hat{z}_0\|, \quad t \geq t_0,$$

which is (28). This proves UGES of (19). \square

Remark 7. Theorem 2 handles marginal modes (those with $\lambda_m \approx 0$) by assigning them fractional weights $\omega_m \in (0, 1)$ rather than forcing a binary stable/unstable classification. Modes closer to instability receive larger weights, while those farther away contribute less to the total “badness budget,” yielding a graded and robust relaxation of classical ADT splits. When mode signs are known and well-separated, the weighted term in (26) may be more conservative than necessary; in such cases one may omit it and recover the standard, less conservative ADT bound with a larger admissible ρ .

5.2. Weighted ADT Stability for Polytopic Systems

The previous subsection established a general weighted ADT stability criterion for the nonlinear impulsive switched system (19) using mode-dependent Lyapunov functions. We now specialize this framework to a subclass of hybrid systems in which the continuous-time dynamics can be decomposed into two components: (i) a linear part that lies in the convex hull of a finite set of matrices, and (ii) a residual nonlinear term that vanishes at the origin and is bounded in norm by the state.

This modeling choice isolates all state-dependent nonlinearities into a single affine perturbation term, while retaining a polytopic structure for the dominant linear dynamics. The polytopic component enables the use of vertex-wise Lyapunov and dissipativity inequalities, whereas the effect of the nonlinear

remainder is controlled through a gain bound. Consequently, the weighted ADT stability conditions can be verified via a finite family of Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMIs), despite the presence of nonlinear and state-dependent terms in the original system.

Assume that the nominal B-equivalent system (19) admits the representation

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\hat{z}}(t) &= A_{\sigma_i}^z(t, \hat{z}(t)) \hat{z}(t) + b_{\sigma_i}^z(t, \hat{z}(t)), \quad t \in [\theta_i, \theta_{i+1}), \\ \hat{z}(\theta_i^+) &= W_{\sigma_{i+1}}^{z, \text{eq}}(\hat{z}(\theta_i^-)), \quad t = \theta_i, \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

where, for each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, the flow matrix admits a convex decomposition

$$A_m^z(t, \hat{z}) = \sum_{r=1}^{v_m} w_{m,r}(t, \hat{z}) A_{m,r}^z, \quad w_{m,r} \geq 0, \quad (30)$$

with vertex matrices $A_{m,r}^z \in \mathbb{R}^{(n-r) \times (n-r)}$ and $\sum_{r=1}^{v_m} w_{m,r} = 1$. We impose no particular structure on the weights $w_{m,r}$ beyond measurability and the simplex constraints above. Assume also that the physical jump map in the state-dependent model Σ_z (i.e., in (3)) is polytopic:

$$J_m^z \in \text{conv}\{J_{m,1}^z, \dots, J_{m,q}^z\}, \quad (31)$$

for some $q \in \mathbb{N}$.

Finally, we assume that the offset term is globally linearly bounded: for each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$ there exists $L_m \geq 0$ such that

$$\|b_m^z(t, \hat{z})\| \leq L_m \|\hat{z}\|, \quad \forall \hat{z} \in \mathbb{R}^{n-r}, \quad \forall t. \quad (32)$$

Moreover, by Remark 2, this offset term vanishes at the origin, i.e., $b_m^z(t, 0) = 0$ for all $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and all t .

Under these assumptions, the following theorem provides a finite set of LMIs whose feasibility, together with the weighted ADT condition (26), guarantees global exponential stability of the nominal B-equivalent internal dynamics.

Theorem 3. *Consider the polytopic affine hybrid system (29) with (30)–(31) and the growth bound (32). For each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$, suppose there exist $P_m \succ 0$, a scalar $\rho_m > 0$, and a scalar $\mu_m \in \mathbb{R}$ such that the following conditions hold:*

(i) *For each vertex $A_{m,r}^z$ of the polytopic flow map,*

$$\begin{bmatrix} (A_{m,r}^z)^\top P_m + P_m A_{m,r}^z - 2\mu_m P_m & P_m & I \\ P_m & -\rho_m^2 I & 0 \\ I & 0 & -I \end{bmatrix} \prec 0. \quad (33)$$

(ii) *The small-gain condition holds:*

$$L_m \rho_m < 1. \quad (34)$$

(iii) *For every transition $\sigma_i \rightarrow \sigma_{i+1}$ and each vertex $J_{\sigma_{i+1},r}^z$ of the jump map, there exists $\beta_{i+1,i} \geq 0$ such that*

$$J_{\sigma_{i+1},r}^z \top P_{\sigma_{i+1}} J_{\sigma_{i+1},r}^z \preceq \beta_{i+1,i} P_{\sigma_i}. \quad (35)$$

Define, for any admissible transition $i \rightarrow j$,

$$\eta_{j,i} := \beta_{j,i} \sup_{\tau \in [\underline{\tau}_i, \bar{\tau}_i]} \exp(2(\mu_i - \mu_j)\tau), \quad (36)$$

and for each mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$,

$$\eta_m := \max_{i: i \rightarrow m} \eta_{m,i}. \quad (37)$$

If the weighted average dwell-time condition (26) holds with

$$\lambda_m := 2\mu_m + \frac{\ln(\eta_m)}{\tau_{a,m}},$$

then there exist constants $c \geq 1$ and $\alpha > 0$ such that every solution of (29) satisfies

$$\|\hat{z}(t)\| \leq c e^{-\alpha(t-t_0)} \|\hat{z}(t_0)\|, \quad \forall t \geq t_0.$$

Consequently, the nominal B-equivalent system (19) is globally exponentially stable.

Proof. Fix a mode $m \in \mathcal{M}$ and suppress the subscript throughout the flow analysis. Define the quadratic Lyapunov function

$$V(\hat{z}) := \hat{z}^\top P \hat{z}.$$

Let $u(t) := b_m^z(t, \hat{z}(t))$ and $y(t) := \hat{z}(t)$. Along the flow (29) we have

$$\dot{y} = A_m^z(t, y) y + u, \quad y = \hat{z}.$$

Fix a vertex A_r^z . Since (33) holds, we have for all y, u ,

$$\begin{bmatrix} y \\ u \end{bmatrix}^\top \begin{bmatrix} (A_r^z)^\top P + P A_r^z - 2\mu P & P & I \\ P & -\rho^2 I & 0 \\ I & 0 & -I \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} y \\ u \end{bmatrix} < 0.$$

Expanding yields

$$y^\top ((A_r^z)^\top P + P A_r^z - 2\mu P) y + 2y^\top P u + 2\|y\|^2 - \rho^2 \|u\|^2 - \|y\|^2 < 0.$$

Noting that $\dot{V}(y) = y^\top ((A_r^z)^\top P + P A_r^z) y + 2y^\top P u$ along $\dot{y} = A_r^z y + u$, we obtain the vertex dissipation inequality

$$\dot{V}(y) \leq 2\mu V(y) + \rho^2 \|u\|^2 - \|y\|^2. \quad (38)$$

Define, for any matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{(n-r) \times (n-r)}$,

$$\mathcal{F}(A) := \begin{bmatrix} A^\top P + P A - 2\mu P & P & I \\ P & -\rho^2 I & 0 \\ I & 0 & -I \end{bmatrix}.$$

Because the map $A \mapsto A^\top P + P A$ is affine, \mathcal{F} is affine:

$$\mathcal{F}\left(\sum_{r=1}^{v_m} w_r A_r^z\right) = \sum_{r=1}^{v_m} w_r \mathcal{F}(A_r^z), \quad \sum_r w_r = 1, \quad w_r \geq 0.$$

By item (i), $\mathcal{F}(A_r^z) \prec 0$ for all vertices r . Since $X \prec 0$ and $Y \prec 0$ imply $\alpha X + (1-\alpha)Y \prec 0$ for all $\alpha \in [0, 1]$,

any convex combination of negative definite matrices is negative definite, hence

$$\mathcal{F}(A_m^z(t, y)) < 0 \quad \forall t, \forall y.$$

Evaluating $\xi^\top \mathcal{F}(A_m^z(t, y)) \xi < 0$ at $\xi = [y^\top \ u^\top \ y^\top]^\top$ gives the inequality

$$\dot{V}(\hat{z}(t)) \leq 2\mu V(\hat{z}(t)) + \rho^2 \|u(t)\|^2 - \|\hat{z}(t)\|^2, \quad (39)$$

for the actual flow matrix $A_m^z(t, y)$.

By (32) and $u = b_m^z(t, \hat{z})$, $\|u(t)\| \leq L\|\hat{z}(t)\|$, hence

$$\rho^2 \|u(t)\|^2 \leq \rho^2 L^2 \|\hat{z}(t)\|^2.$$

Substituting into (39) yields

$$\dot{V}(\hat{z}(t)) \leq 2\mu V(\hat{z}(t)) - (1 - \rho^2 L^2) \|\hat{z}(t)\|^2.$$

The small-gain condition (34) implies $\rho^2 L^2 < 1$, so $1 - \rho^2 L^2 > 0$ and therefore

$$\dot{V}(\hat{z}(t)) \leq 2\mu V(\hat{z}(t)). \quad (40)$$

Integrating (40) over any interval $[t_1, t_2]$ (with $t_2 \geq t_1$) gives the forward-time bound

$$V(\Phi_m^z(t_2, t_1, z)) \leq e^{2\mu(t_2-t_1)} V(z). \quad (41)$$

By exchanging (t_1, t_2) in (41) one also gets the backward-time bound (when $t_2 \geq t_1$)

$$V(\Phi_m^z(t_1, t_2, z)) \leq e^{-2\mu(t_2-t_1)} V(z). \quad (42)$$

Consider an admissible transition $i \rightarrow j$ at time θ_i , with the associated B-equivalent map (17). Let $\tau := \xi_i - \theta_i \in [\underline{\tau}_i, \bar{\tau}_i]$ and define

$$\begin{aligned} z^- &:= \hat{z}(\theta_i^-), & z_i(\xi_i) &:= \Phi_i^z(\xi_i, \theta_i, z^-), \\ z^+ &:= \hat{z}(\theta_i^+) = W_j^z(s(\theta_i), z^-). \end{aligned}$$

Then, by (17),

$$z^+ = \Phi_j^z(\theta_i, \xi_i, J_j^z(s(\xi_i^-), z_i(\xi_i))).$$

Fix the transition $i \rightarrow j$. For each jump vertex $J_{j,r}^z$, condition (35) gives

$$x^\top (J_{j,r}^z)^\top P_j J_{j,r}^z x \leq \beta_{j,i} x^\top P_i x, \quad \forall x,$$

i.e.

$$\|P_j^{1/2} J_{j,r}^z P_i^{-1/2}\|_2 \leq \sqrt{\beta_{j,i}}.$$

Now let $J_j^z = \sum_{r=1}^q \alpha_r J_{j,r}^z$ with $\alpha_r \geq 0$, $\sum_r \alpha_r = 1$. By the triangle inequality,

$$\begin{aligned} \|P_j^{1/2} J_j^z P_i^{-1/2}\|_2 &= \left\| \sum_{r=1}^q \alpha_r P_j^{1/2} J_{j,r}^z P_i^{-1/2} \right\|_2 \\ &\leq \sum_{r=1}^q \alpha_r \|P_j^{1/2} J_{j,r}^z P_i^{-1/2}\|_2 \\ &\leq \sqrt{\beta_{j,i}}. \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, for all x ,

$$V_j(J_j^z x) = x^\top (J_j^z)^\top P_j J_j^z x \leq \beta_{j,i} x^\top P_i x = \beta_{j,i} V_i(x). \quad (43)$$

Apply the flow bounds (41)–(42) in modes i and j :

$$V_i(z_i(\xi_i)) = V_i(\Phi_i^z(\xi_i, \theta_i, z^-)) \leq e^{2\mu_i \tau} V_i(z^-),$$

and, using (43) with $x = z_i(\xi_i)$,

$$\begin{aligned} V_j\left(J_j^z(s(\xi_i^-), z_i(\xi_i))\right) &\leq \beta_{j,i} V_i(z_i(\xi_i)) \\ &\leq \beta_{j,i} e^{2\mu_i \tau} V_i(z^-). \end{aligned}$$

Finally, the post-jump flow from ξ_i to θ_i is backward in time, hence by (42) in mode j ,

$$\begin{aligned} V_j(z^+) &= V_j\left(\Phi_j^z(\theta_i, \xi_i, J_j^z(s(\xi_i^-), z_i(\xi_i)))\right) \\ &\leq e^{-2\mu_j \tau} V_j\left(J_j^z(s(\xi_i^-), z_i(\xi_i))\right). \end{aligned}$$

Combining the last three inequalities yields, for all $\tau \in [\underline{\tau}_i, \bar{\tau}_i]$,

$$V_j(z^+) \leq \beta_{j,i} e^{2(\mu_i - \mu_j)\tau} V_i(z^-).$$

Taking the supremum over the admissible dwell-time interval gives

$$\begin{aligned} V_j(\hat{z}(\theta_i^+)) &\leq \eta_{j,i} V_i(\hat{z}(\theta_i^-)), \\ \eta_{j,i} &:= \beta_{j,i} \sup_{\tau \in [\underline{\tau}_i, \bar{\tau}_i]} \exp(2(\mu_i - \mu_j)\tau), \end{aligned}$$

which is (24). For each mode m , define $\eta_m := \max_{i: i \rightarrow m} \eta_{m,i}$ and set $\lambda_m := 2\mu_m + \ln(\eta_m)/\tau_{a,m}$.

Because $P_m > 0$, the functions $V_m(\hat{z}) = \hat{z}^\top P_m \hat{z}$ satisfy the comparison bound (27) for suitable class- \mathcal{K} functions \underline{v}, \bar{v} . Moreover, (40) provides the flow inequality (23) with rate $2\mu_m$, and (36) and (37) provide the jump comparison (24) with gains $\eta_{j,i}$ and η_m . Thus all hypotheses of Theorem 2 hold. The claim follows from Theorem 2. \square

The representation in (29), inspired by polytopic LPV modeling methods [24], readily adapts to many physical systems, e.g., mechanical systems [25], chemical and process reactors [26], power electronics [27], and robotics [28]. In these applications, the scheduling variables are typically measurable (or admit a measurable low-dimensional parametrization) and evolve within known compact sets. This enables the nonlinear dynamics to be embedded into, or approximated by, a finite family of linear models blended via convex weights, yielding a polytopic dependence of the form $A(\vartheta) \in \text{conv}\{A_r\}$ for ϑ constrained to a known set. For automated procedures to construct such polytopic LPV representations, see [24].

For the final part of the section, we propose a search procedure (Algorithm 1) which, for the polytopic system (29) and a linear SISO sliding manifold $s_m(x) = C_m x$ with $C_m \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$, attempts to synthesize matrices C_m such that

(i) an objective function for λ_m is satisfied, for example $J(\{\lambda_m\}) = \sum_{m \in \mathcal{M}} \omega_m \max\{\lambda_m, 0\}$, $\omega_m \propto \frac{1}{\tau_{a,m}}$, with feasibility certified via the LMIs (33) and (35); and

(ii) the closed-loop dynamics satisfy the no-beating condition (5) during both reaching and practical sliding.

Starting from an initial set $\{C_m\}_{m \in \mathcal{M}}$, the algorithm first checks condition (5) for all modes on a compact domain, e.g. for (s, z, u) satisfying $\|z\| \leq R^z$, $\|s\| \leq \Delta^*$, and $u \in \bar{U}_m$. If the condition is violated for some mode m , the corresponding row vector $C_m \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times n}$ is updated by a small rotation in \mathbb{R}^n until no beating is certified on the prescribed domain. Next, the chosen objective function $J(\{\lambda_m\})$ is evaluated. If it is not satisfied, the sliding manifold associated with the mode having the worst decay rate λ_m is greedily updated via further such rotations, and the procedure is repeated until both requirements are met or a termination criterion is reached.

6. Simulation Results

Consider $x = [x_1 \ x_2 \ x_3]^\top$ and $(u_k, d_k^{\text{ext}}, d_k^\Delta) \in \mathbb{R}$ with initial condition $x_0 = [0.3, 0.4, 0.5]^\top$. For all $i \in \mathbb{N}$:

Mode 1

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= (-1.2 + 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_1 + (0.5 + 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_2 \\ &\quad + (0.25 - 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_3 + 0.35 \tanh(0.7x_1 + 0.2x_2) \\ &\quad + 0.15 \sin(x_3) \tanh(x_2), \\ \dot{x}_2 &= (0.5 - 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_1 + (-1.15 - 0.15 \tanh(x_1)) x_2 \\ &\quad + (0.45 + 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_3 + 0.25 \tanh(0.4x_1 - 0.6x_2) \\ &\quad + 0.10 \sin(x_1) \tanh(0.5x_3), \\ \dot{x}_3 &= (0.15 + 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_1 + (0.25 + 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_2 \\ &\quad + (-1.0 + 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_3 + 0.30 \tanh(0.6x_1 + 0.6x_2) \\ &\quad + 0.20 \sin(x_1) \tanh(x_3) + u_1^c + d_1^{\text{ext}} + d_1^\Delta. \end{aligned} \quad (44)$$

Mode 2

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= (-0.8 + 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_1 + (0.3 - 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_2 \\ &\quad + (0.3 + 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_3 + 0.30 \tanh(0.5x_2 - 0.3x_1) \\ &\quad + 0.10 \sin(0.7x_3) \tanh(x_1), \\ \dot{x}_2 &= (0.15 + 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_1 + (-1.5 - 0.1 \tanh(x_1)) x_2 \\ &\quad + (0.35 - 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_3 + 0.35 \tanh(0.4x_1 + 0.4x_2) \\ &\quad + 0.10 \sin(x_2) \tanh(0.5x_3), \\ \dot{x}_3 &= (0.15 - 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_1 + (0.15 + 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_2 \\ &\quad + (-0.65 + 0.05 \tanh(x_1)) x_3 + 0.25 \tanh(0.6x_2 - 0.2x_1) \\ &\quad + 0.25 \sin(x_2) \tanh(x_3) + u_2^c + d_2^{\text{ext}} + d_2^\Delta. \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

The anchors are defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_i &= 0.9 \lfloor \frac{i+1}{2} \rfloor + 3 \lfloor \frac{i}{2} \rfloor, \\ \xi_i &= \theta_i + \tau_{2-(i \bmod 2)}(x), \quad \forall i \in \mathbb{N}, \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where $\lfloor \cdot \rfloor$ denotes the floor operator.

The discontinuity surfaces for both modes are defined as $\tau_1(x) = \min\{0.5x_2^4, \bar{\tau}_1\}$, $\tau_2(x) =$

Algorithm 1: Design of $s_m(x) = C_m x$

Input: Modes \mathcal{M} , vertices $A_{m,r}^z$, affine terms b_m^z , weights $w_{m,r}$, jumps $J_{m,r}$, timers τ_m , wADT data, $\tau_{a,m}$, state bounds R^z, Δ^* , input bounds $\{\bar{U}_m\}_{m \in \mathcal{M}}$, max iters N_{\max}

Output: $\{C_m\}_{m \in \mathcal{M}}$

```

1 foreach  $m \in \mathcal{M}$  do
2   |  $P_m \leftarrow I$ ; pick nonzero  $C_m$ 
3 for  $k = 1 : N_{\max}$  do
4   | for each  $m \in \mathcal{M}$  do
5     | solve LMIs (33), (35) w.r.t.  $(P_m, C_m)$ ;
6     | compute  $\mu_m$  and  $\eta_{j,i}$ ;
7     | test no-beating on the compact domain
8     |  $\{\|z\| \leq R^z, \|s\| \leq \Delta^*, |u| \leq \bar{U}_m\}$ ;
9     |  $\mathcal{B} \leftarrow \{m : \text{no-beating violated}\}$ ;
10    | if  $\mathcal{B} \neq \emptyset$  then
11      | foreach  $m \in \mathcal{B}$  do
12        | while rotation budget not exhausted
13          | and  $m$  violates no-beating do
14            | update  $C_m$  by a small rotation in
15            |  $\mathbb{R}^n$ ;
16            | re-solve LMIs of  $m$  and its incident
17            | jumps;
18          | continue
19        | For each  $m$ :  $\eta_m \leftarrow \max_i \eta_{m,i}$ ;
20        |  $\lambda_m \leftarrow 2\mu_m + \log(\eta_m)/\tau_{a,m}$ ;
21        | if objective  $(\{\lambda_m\})$  is satisfied then
22          | return  $\{C_m\}$ 
23        | pick  $m^* \in \arg \max \lambda_m$ ;
24        | while rotation budget not exhausted do
25          | propose small rotation of  $C_{m^*}$  in  $\mathbb{R}^n$ ;
26          | re-solve LMIs of  $m^*$  and its incident
27          | jumps;
28          | if no-beating holds and objective  $(\{\lambda_m\})$ 
29          | improved then
30            | accept new  $C_{m^*}$ ;
31 Fail: no suitable  $\{C_m\}$  within  $N_{\max}$ ;

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$\min\{0.1x_2^4, \bar{\tau}_2\}$. Moreover, $\tau_k = 0.001$, $\bar{\tau}_k = 0.5$, $k \in \{1, 2\}$.

The switching sequence is $\sigma = \{2, 1, \dots\}$, i.e., it starts in mode 2 and then alternates. The average dwell times are $\tau_{a,1} = 1$ and $\tau_{a,2} = 3$.

The jump matrices are identical across modes,

$$x(\xi_i^+) = J_1 x(\xi_i^-) = J_2 x(\xi_i^-) = \begin{bmatrix} 1.3 & 0.9 & 0 \\ 1.5 & 1.2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} x(\xi_i^-), \quad (47)$$

and the jump map has a single vertex.

The matched model uncertainty d_k^Δ satisfies

$$d_1^\Delta = -4x_2, \quad d_2^\Delta = x_1 + 3x_2 + 5x_1^2.$$

Assuming $\|x\| \leq 0.75$, the maximum matched uncertainty is bounded by $|d_k^\Delta| < 4.69$, $k \in \{1, 2\}$.

The exogenous disturbance d_k^{ext} is a continuous zero-mean colored Gaussian process with correlation

time $\tau_c = 2$ s and intensity $P = 0.5$. Its magnitude is bounded by $|d_k^{\text{ext}}| < 1.58$, $k \in \{1, 2\}$, yielding a combined worst-case disturbance bound $\bar{D} = 6.27$ for both modes.

The sliding manifold for mode $k \in \{1, 2\}$ is $s_k(x) = C_k x$, with $C_k \in \mathbb{R}^{1 \times 3}$ and $C_k = [c_{k,1}, c_{k,2}, c_{k,3}]$. For each mode we choose an internal coordinate $z_k \in \mathbb{R}^2$ by selecting a matrix $V_k \in \mathbb{R}^{2 \times 3}$ whose rows form a basis of $\ker C_k$, and define $T_k := [C_k^\top \ V_k^\top]^\top$, $[s_k \ z_k^\top]^\top = T_k x$, so that T_k is invertible. On the sliding manifold $s_k = 0$, the state can be written as $x = T_k^{-1} [0 \ z_k^\top]^\top =: H_k z_k$, $H_k \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times 2}$.

The control input in mode (k) is decomposed as

$$u_k^c(t) = u_k^{\text{eq}}(s, z, t) + u_k^n(s, z, t),$$

where the equivalent control u_k^{eq} is chosen so that $\dot{s}_k(x, t) = 0$ for the nominal system (i.e., $d_k^\Delta = 0$, $d_k^{\text{ext}} = 0$). The sliding condition $\dot{s}_k = C_k \dot{x} = 0$ gives, on the manifold $s_k = 0$,

$$\begin{aligned} u_k^{\text{eq}}(0, z, t) &= - \frac{\nabla s_k f_k(x, t)|_{x=H_k z}}{\nabla s_k g} \\ &= - \frac{1}{c_{k,3}} \nabla s_k f_k(x, t)|_{x=H_k z}, \end{aligned}$$

since $g = [0, 0, 1]^\top$ implies $\nabla s_k g = C_k g = c_{k,3}$.

The discontinuous correction term is

$$u_k^n(s, z, t) = - \frac{\kappa}{c_{k,3}} |s|^{0.1} \text{sat}\left(\frac{s_k}{\Delta}\right), \quad k \in \{1, 2\},$$

and the control amplitude is hard-saturated as $|u_k^c(t)| \leq \bar{U}^c$, $\bar{U}^c = 8.5$.

Under the equivalent control, the nominal internal dynamics on the sliding manifold, in coordinates z_k , satisfy $\dot{z} = f_{\sigma(t)}^{z, \text{eq}}(z, t)$ for each mode $k \in \{1, 2\}$,

$$f_k^{z, \text{eq}}(z, t) = V_k P_k^{\text{proj}} f_k^{\text{eq}}(x, t)|_{x=H_k z}, \quad (48)$$

where $P_k^{\text{proj}} := I - g(C_k g)^{-1} C_k$ is the standard sliding projector.

To obtain a polytopic representation of (48), set $w_1(z) = \frac{1}{2}(1 + \tanh(h_k z))$, $w_2(z) = 1 - w_1(z)$, where $h_k := e_1 H_k$. Then each $f_k^{z, \text{eq}}$ can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} f_1^{z, \text{eq}}(z, t) &= w_1(z) V_1 P_1^{\text{proj}} \begin{bmatrix} -1.1 & 0.6 & 0.2 \\ 0.4 & -1.3 & 0.5 \\ 0.2 & 0.3 & -0.9 \end{bmatrix} H_1 \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ w_2(z) V_1 P_1^{\text{proj}} \begin{bmatrix} -1.3 & 0.4 & 0.3 \\ 0.6 & -1.0 & 0.4 \\ 0.1 & 0.2 & -1.1 \end{bmatrix} H_1 \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ V_1 P_1^{\text{proj}} b_1(x) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f_2^{z, \text{eq}}(z, t) &= w_1(z) V_2 P_2^{\text{proj}} \begin{bmatrix} -0.7 & 0.2 & 0.4 \\ 0.2 & -1.6 & 0.3 \\ 0.1 & 0.2 & -0.6 \end{bmatrix} H_2 \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ w_2(z) V_2 P_2^{\text{proj}} \begin{bmatrix} -0.9 & 0.4 & 0.2 \\ 0.1 & -1.4 & 0.4 \\ 0.2 & 0.1 & -0.7 \end{bmatrix} H_2 \begin{bmatrix} z_1 \\ z_2 \end{bmatrix} \\ &+ V_2 P_2^{\text{proj}} b_2(x) \end{aligned}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} b_1(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.35 \tanh(0.7x_1 + 0.2x_2) + 0.15 \sin(x_3) \tanh(x_2) \\ 0.25 \tanh(0.4x_1 - 0.6x_2) + 0.10 \sin(x_1) \tanh(0.5x_3) \\ 0.30 \tanh(0.6x_1 + 0.6x_2) + 0.20 \sin(x_1) \tanh(x_3) \end{bmatrix}, \\ b_2(x) &= \begin{bmatrix} 0.30 \tanh(0.5x_2 - 0.3x_1) + 0.10 \sin(0.7x_3) \tanh(x_1) \\ 0.35 \tanh(0.4x_1 + 0.4x_2) + 0.10 \sin(x_2) \tanh(0.5x_3) \\ 0.25 \tanh(0.6x_2 - 0.2x_1) + 0.25 \sin(x_2) \tanh(x_3) \end{bmatrix}, \end{aligned}$$

and

$$P_k^{\text{proj}} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\frac{c_{k,1}}{c_{k,3}} & -\frac{c_{k,2}}{c_{k,3}} & 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Starting from $C_1 = C_2 = [1 \ 1 \ 1]/\|[1 \ 1 \ 1]\|$ and minimizing $J(\lambda_m) = \lambda_1/\tau_{a,1} + \lambda_2/\tau_{a,2}$, Algorithm 1 returns

$$\begin{aligned} C_1 &= [0.7274 \quad -0.3637 \quad 0.5819], \\ C_2 &= [-0.5392 \quad 0.5392 \quad -0.6470], \end{aligned}$$

with $\mu_1 = -0.2869$, $\mu_2 = -0.5937$, $\beta_{12} = 5.4282$, $\beta_{21} = 8.8871$, $\rho_1 = 2.8057$, $\rho_2 = 3.7023$, $\eta_{12} = 5.4248$, $\eta_{21} = 12.0775$, $\lambda_1 = 1.1172$, $\lambda_2 = -0.3569$, and

$$P_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.7116 & 0.1997 \\ 0.1997 & 0.2884 \end{bmatrix}, P_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1.5023 & 0.4356 \\ 0.4356 & 0.4977 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Choosing $\delta = 0.34$ yields $S = \{2\}$, $U = \{1\}$, $M = \emptyset$. Since $\lambda_U^{\text{max}} = 1.1172$, the wADT constraint requires $\rho > \lambda_U^{\text{max}}/\delta = 3.2859$. We take $\rho = 3.30$, $\gamma = 0$, so the inequality reduces to $3.30 \leq T_S/T_U$.

From (46), the period of the switching signal is 3.9s, with dwell times 3s in the stable mode and 0.9s in the unstable mode. Hence, if t_f denotes the final simulation time, then $T_S = (3/3.9)t_f$, $T_U = (0.9/3.9)t_f$, so $T_S/T_U \approx 3.33$, which satisfies the wADT condition.

The disturbance-related parameters in Theorem 1 are $\Phi_1^{\text{max}} = 3.6478$ and $\Phi_2^{\text{max}} = 4.0558$. Using the hyperplane $s(x) = Cx$ and the linear jump map $x^+ = Jx$, Corollary 1 gives $\alpha_1 = 0.3569$, $\alpha_2 = 0.4745$, $\beta_1 = 0.4302$, $\beta_2 = 0.4250$, so $\alpha_s = \max\{\alpha_1, \alpha_2\} = 0.4745$, $\beta_s = \max\{\beta_1, \beta_2\} = 0.4302$.

With $\underline{\vartheta}_1 = \bar{\vartheta}_1 = c_{1,3} = 0.5819$, $\underline{\vartheta}_2 = \bar{\vartheta}_2 = c_{2,3} = 0.6470$, $\underline{\theta} = 0.9$, the bound (10) yields $\underline{U}^n \geq 8.11$ for $\Delta = 10^{-3}$, $\underline{U}^n \geq 7.84$ for $\Delta = 0.1$.

The term λ_s evaluates to $\lambda_s = 1.19$ for $\Delta = 10^{-3}$ and $\lambda_s = 1.01$ for $\Delta = 0.1$, giving $\kappa_s = 10.47$ for $\Delta = 10^{-3}$, and $\kappa_s = 6.38$ for $\Delta = 0.1$.

To verify the no-beating condition, Assumption **(B3)** must hold. Using $\Delta^* = \alpha_s \Delta + \beta_s$, we obtain $\Delta^* = 0.43$ for $\Delta = 10^{-3}$ and $\Delta^* = 0.47$ for $\Delta = 0.1$.

The test was performed over $\|s\| \leq \Delta^*$, $\|z\| \leq 0.75$, with the bounds 8) and $|d_k^\Delta(t) + d_k^{\text{ext}}(t)| \leq 6.27$. Substituting $x = T^{-1}[s \ z^\top]^\top$ into (44)–(45) and the jump map (47), the quantity in (5) was evaluated on a uniform grid and remained strictly positive over the entire set. Hence, no beating occurs during reaching or sliding.

In Fig. 3, the state trajectories and control input are shown for two cases: $\Delta = 0.001$ and $\Delta = 0.1$. As seen in Figs. 3(a)–(b), when the boundary layer is tight ($\Delta = 0.001$), the system states converge to zero within approximately 12 seconds. After this point, the states remain at zero and almost no further jumps occur (as expected since $x^+ = Jx^-$ and when $x^- \approx 0$, $x^+ \approx 0$). However, the control input exhibits chattering, which is quantitatively reflected in its total variation $\text{TV}(u) = 455.74$.

In contrast, for $\Delta = 0.1$ (Figs. 3(d)–(f)), the states do not converge exactly to zero but fluctuate around it within the tube, which leads to additional jumps. The control input, however, is smoother, as evidenced by its smaller total variation ($\text{TV}(u) = 53.49$). Fig. 4 shows the trajectory of s for $\Delta = 0.1$. As expected, $s(x)$ remains close to, but not exactly on the sliding manifold, and the jumps in $s(x)$ are clearly visible. After each jump, s departs from the manifold only transiently before being re-attracted by the control. The use of mode-dependent sliding variables provides additional flexibility, since $s(x)$ is not required to follow a single continuous path toward the origin across modes. Small oscillations near $s = 0$ reflect the practical (rather than exact) convergence ensured by the design. In Fig. 5, the state trajectory is shown in (x_1, x_2) -space together with the discontinuity surfaces positioned between anchors θ_i . Each surface is crossed exactly once, and no beating is observed, consistent with the no-beating condition enforced during the sliding-manifold design.

7. Conclusion

A practical sliding-mode control framework was developed for nonlinear state-dependent impulsive switched systems. Using mode-dependent sliding manifolds and continuous reaching laws, a lower bound on the control input was obtained that guarantees reachability and invariance of a prescribed sliding tube despite state-dependent jumps. A tailored B-equivalent time-dependent model was introduced, and mode-dependent weighted average dwell-time conditions ensuring global exponential stability were derived. For internal dynamics representable as convex combinations of linear subsystems, LMI certificates were provided. An associated algorithm was proposed for systematic construction of sliding manifolds ensuring practical stability and absence of beating. Numerical results confirmed the effectiveness of the approach. Future directions include extending the framework to autonomous discontinuous systems of the form $\dot{x} = f(x)$ with jump surfaces $\gamma(x) = 0$.

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References

- [1] S. Trenn and F. Wirth, “Linear switched daes: Lyapunov exponents, a converse lyapunov theorem, and barabanov norms,” in *2012 IEEE 51st IEEE Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*. IEEE, 2012, pp. 2666–2671.
- [2] Z. Xu, X. Li, and V. Stojanovic, “Exponential stability of nonlinear state-dependent delayed impulsive systems with applications,” *Nonlinear Analysis: Hybrid Systems*, vol. 42, p. 101088, 2021.
- [3] S. G. Nersesov and W. M. Haddad, “Finite-time stabilization of nonlinear impulsive dynamical systems,” *Nonlinear Analysis: Hybrid Systems*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 832–845, 2008.
- [4] X. Li and D. Yang, “Stabilization of impulsive switched systems: State-dependent switching approach,” *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics: Systems*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 1094–1103, 2023.
- [5] M. A. Nojournian, M. Ayati, and M. R. Zakerzadeh, “Asynchronous bumpless stabilisation of uncertain switched linear positive systems with mixed time delay and 1 1-gain performance,” *IET Control Theory & Applications*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 151–165, 2022.
- [6] F. Küsters, M. G.-M. Ruppert, and S. Trenn, “Controllability of switched differential-algebraic equations,” *Systems & Control Letters*, vol. 78, pp. 32–39, 2015.
- [7] N. Kalamian, H. Khaloozadeh, and S. M. Ayati, “Adaptive state-dependent impulsive observer design for nonlinear deterministic and stochastic dynamics with time-delays,” *ISA transactions*, vol. 98, pp. 87–100, 2020.
- [8] N. Kalamain, H. Khaloozadeh, and M. Ayati, “On design of adaptive impulsive observer based on comparison system: Modifications in stability theory and feasibility centralization,” *International Journal of Dynamics and Control*, vol. 11, no. 1, pp. 149–161, 2023.
- [9] M. A. Nojournian, M. R. Zakerzadeh, and M. Ayati, “Observer-based controller of uncertain switching positive linear systems: a unilaterally tracking scheme,” *Asian Journal of Control*, vol. 25, no. 3, pp. 1957–1970, 2023.
- [10] —, “Stabilization of delayed switched positive nonlinear systems under mode dependent average dwell time: A bumpless control scheme,” *Nonlinear Analysis: Hybrid Systems*, vol. 47, p. 101300, 2023.
- [11] X. Lv and X. Li, “Finite time stability and controller design for nonlinear impulsive sampled-data systems with applications,” *ISA transactions*, vol. 70, pp. 30–36, 2017.
- [12] M. Akhmet, *Principles of discontinuous dynamical systems*. Springer Science & Business Media, 2010.
- [13] X. Zhang, C. Li, and T. Huang, “Hybrid impulsive and switching hopfield neural networks with state-dependent impulses,” *Neural Networks*, vol. 93, pp. 176–184, 2017.
- [14] W. Ren and J. Xiong, “Stability analysis of impulsive switched time-delay systems with state-dependent impulses,” *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 64, no. 9, pp. 3928–3935, 2019.
- [15] I. Rachunkov’a and J. Tomevcek, “State-dependent impulses,” *Boundary Value Problems on Compact Interval*, vol. 6, 2015.
- [16] W.-H. Chen, X. Deng, and W. X. Zheng, “Sliding-mode control for linear uncertain systems with impulse effects via switching gains,” *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 67, no. 4, pp. 2044–2051, 2021.
- [17] X. Li and Y. Zhao, “Sliding mode control for linear impulsive systems with matched disturbances,” *IEEE Transactions on Automatic Control*, vol. 67, no. 11, pp. 6203–6210, 2021.
- [18] X. Zhang, “Robust integral sliding mode control for uncertain switched systems under arbitrary switching rules,” *Nonlinear Analysis: Hybrid Systems*, vol. 37, p. 100900, 2020.
- [19] X. Su, X. Liu, P. Shi, and Y.-D. Song, “Sliding mode control of hybrid switched systems via an event-triggered mechanism,” *automatica*, vol. 90, pp. 294–303, 2018.
- [20] A. K. Pour, S. Trenn, M. Ayati, and M. R. Zakerzadeh, “Funnel-based output tracking control for nonlinear im-

Figure 3: State trajectories and control input: (a)–(c) correspond to $\Delta = 0.001$, and (d)–(f) correspond to $\Delta = 0.1$.

Figure 4: Evolution of the sliding variable for $\Delta = 0.1$.

Figure 5: Trajectory of the system together with discontinuity surfaces.

pulsive switched systems,” *Nonlinear Analysis: Hybrid Systems*, vol. 60, p. 101661, 2026.

- [21] A. K. Pour and S. Trenn, “Funnel control for impulsive switched systems,” in *2024 IEEE 63rd Conference on Decision and Control (CDC)*. IEEE, 2024, pp. 7810–7815.
- [22] W. M. Haddad, V. Chellaboina, and S. G. Nersisov, “Impulsive and hybrid dynamical systems: stability, dissipativity, and control,” in *Impulsive and hybrid dynamical systems*. Princeton University Press, 2014.
- [23] R. Goebel, R. G. Sanfelice, and A. R. Teel, “Hybrid dynamical systems,” *IEEE control systems magazine*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 28–93, 2009.
- [24] D. Rotondo, V. Puig, F. Nejjari, and M. Witczak, “Automated generation and comparison of takagi–sugeno and polytopic quasi-lpv models,” *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, vol. 277, pp. 44–64, 2015.
- [25] T.-V.-A. Nguyen, B.-T. Dong, and N.-T. Bui, “Enhancing stability control of inverted pendulum using takagi–sugeno fuzzy model with disturbance rejection and input–output constraints,” *Scientific Reports*, vol. 13, no. 1, p. 14412, 2023.
- [26] N. N. Lima, L. Z. Linan, D. N. Melo, F. Manenti, R. Maciel Filho, M. Embiruçu, and M. R. W. Maciel, “Nonlinear fuzzy identification of batch polymerization processes,” in *Computer Aided Chemical Engineering*. Elsevier, 2015, vol. 37, pp. 599–604.
- [27] M. F. Coradini, L. H. V. Felão, S. d. S. Lyra, M. C. M. Teixeira, and C. Kitano, “Takagi–sugeno fuzzy nonlinear control system for optical interferometry,” *Sensors*, vol. 25, no. 6, p. 1853, 2025.
- [28] M. Q. Zaman and H.-M. Wu, “Genetic algorithm based takagi-sugeno fuzzy modelling of a mecanum wheeled mobile robot,” *International Journal of Control, Automation and Systems*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 907–919, 2025.